

Pilot Evaluation, including ENTS Pilot Factsheets

Deliverable 1.3

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable 1.3, “Pilot Evaluation, including ENTS Pilot Factsheets” presents a comprehensive assessment of the seven nature-based solution (NBS) pilots implemented under the MULTISOURCE project. Moving beyond the monitoring focus of Deliverable 1.2, this report synthesizes insights from across the pilot sites to reflect on design performance, treatment outcomes, co-benefits, challenges, and lessons learned for future implementations. The evaluation integrates findings from several work packages (WP1–WP5), providing a multi-dimensional perspective on the pilots’ technical, environmental, and social impacts: hydraulic and treatment performance data (WP1), risk assessments (WP2), business model analyses (WP3), and life cycle and co-benefit assessments (WP4). The report combines both quantitative and qualitative findings and is structured around cross-cutting discussion sections accompanied by individual pilot factsheets. Each pilot is examined through a harmonized factsheet and analyzed in relation to system typology, pollutant removal, risk reduction, and reuse readiness. While systems differ in influent type and local objectives, common themes emerged, such as the value of modular designs, stakeholder engagement, and monitoring technologies.

The accompanying pilot factsheets are intended for a broad audience, from researchers and water professionals to planners and citizens. They summarize each system’s design and performance, supporting replication and knowledge transfer. Datasets will be made available via Zenodo, and scientific publications are underway to extend the project’s legacy beyond its formal end.

All pilots were operational for at least one year, and most of them for over two years, allowing for the observation of seasonal variations and a range of operational conditions. The evaluation confirms that the pilots generally met their primary treatment objectives, whether for greywater reuse, stormwater control, or combined sewer overflow (CSO) mitigation, while also delivering significant co-benefits such as biodiversity enhancement, climate adaptation, and public engagement.

Key findings include:

- High treatment efficiency for conventional pollutants (TSS, BOD, COD), with several pilots achieving over 90% removal.
- Variable but promising performance on nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), heavy metals, organic micropollutants, and microplastics, with systems showing adaptability through hybridization or post-treatment additions (e.g. ozonation).
- Demonstrated pathogen reduction in multiple pilots, supporting safe water reuse for toilet flushing and irrigation.
- Measurable co-benefits including educational outreach, temperature mitigation, increased green cover, and stakeholder engagement, essential to urban acceptance and NBS mainstreaming.
- Operational robustness in both temperate and cold climates, with strategic design adaptations such as effluent recirculation, modular configurations, and smart aeration.

Challenges encountered include infrastructure constraints, stakeholder dependency for monitoring, limited reuse infrastructure, and regulatory misalignment, particularly for decentralized reuse schemes. Lessons learned emphasize the need for flexible design, clear ownership models, and co-designed implementation strategies with local actors.

This deliverable contributes to the formulation of design and replication guidance (linked to WP4 Nat4Wat tool and book), supporting the wider uptake of NBS in European and international contexts. The accompanying pilot factsheets provide accessible, transferable knowledge for practitioners, planners, citizens and policymakers, facilitating technology sharing and cross-fertilization within and beyond the MULTISOURCE network.

1 MULTISOURCE ENTS Pilots

WP1 of the MULTISOURCE project encompasses all pilot-related activities, including the demonstration and optimization of nature-based solutions (NBS) through three key tasks: T1.1 (Pilot monitoring, including real-time monitoring options, M1–M40), T1.2 (Participatory methods for quantifying co-benefits, M10–M40), and T1.3 (Pilot evaluation, M36–M48). The project includes seven pilot sites, six in European countries and one in the United States, each implementing a technically innovative NBS tailored to specific urban water management challenges. Collectively, these pilots demonstrate the versatility and multifunctionality of NBS, targeting a broad range of influent types, including raw domestic wastewater, greywater, road runoff, and combined sewer overflows.

Each pilot is implemented as a decentralized, site-specific system, offering valuable insights into the performance, integration, and replicability of NBS in real-world conditions. The systems vary in size, configuration, and local objectives, but share a common emphasis on sustainability, adaptability, and co-benefit delivery. D1.3 builds upon the data presented in D1.2, shifting the focus from individual pilot monitoring results to a broader, integrated synthesis of design configurations, treatment efficiencies, co-benefits, and operational performance.

This deliverable summarizes the pilot most relevant findings through synthetic yet comprehensive factsheets that serve as tools for immediate dissemination to diverse audiences. While the pilots are not evaluated through direct comparison, due to differences in influent types, regulatory frameworks, and treatment goals, this report identifies shared insights, common design strategies, and recurring implementation challenges. These cross-cutting findings provide strategic guidance for future deployment and scaling of NBS in urban environments.

1.1 Overview of Coordinated Work and Evaluation Framing

Activities were structured around three main tasks: T1.1 (monitoring), T1.2 (co-benefit quantification), and T1.3 (pilot evaluation). Monitoring plans, data collection protocols, and co-benefit assessment methodologies were collaboratively developed to ensure alignment of research and development goals while accommodating the specific conditions and objectives of each pilot site. This coordinated effort established the foundation for the structured synthesis presented in Deliverable D1.3.

Rather than offering a direct comparison of the seven pilot systems, each of which treats different water types under varying regulatory and climatic conditions, this deliverable draws out key cross-cutting insights based on thematic evaluation. The analysis focuses on:

- The diversity of system designs and their alignment with local treatment and reuse objectives;
- The range of pollutant groups addressed and general trends in treatment performance;
- The delivery of environmental and social co-benefits, including biodiversity enhancement, public education, and climate resilience;
- Implementation, monitoring, and operational challenges that influence long-term feasibility.

Each pilot is examined individually, while overarching reflections contribute to positioning nature-based solutions as adaptable and replicable strategies for integrated urban water management.

By mid-2024, six of the seven pilots had completed at least 18 months of data collection, with several exceeding two years of continuous operation. The monitoring period ranges are reported in Table 1.1. The findings presented in D1.3 (M47) combine quantitative performance metrics with qualitative insights from implementation and system operation.

Table 1.1 Timeline of the MULTISOURCE monitoring efforts.

Pilot	Start date	Stop date
Pilot 1: France - INRAE - Rhizosph'air pilot treating raw domestic wastewater	November 2022	August 2024
Pilot 2: USA - MSU – Vertical flow wetland treating high-strength wastewater	January 2022	June 2024
Pilot 3: Belgium - Rietland - Phytoparking treating pre-treated wastewater	May 2022	November 2023
Pilot 4: Italy - IRIDRA – Hybrid treatment wetland treating CSO	June 2022	July 2024
Pilot 5: Spain - ICRA - Greenwall treating greywater	May 2023	May 2025
Pilot 6: NIVA/Oslo Municipality - Raingarden treating road runoff	October 2022	September 2024
Pilot 7: Germany - UFZ - Green roof rainwater	April 2022	August 2023

2. ENTS Pilot Factsheets

This section compiles the factsheets of the seven MULTISOURCE ENTS pilots implemented across six European countries and the United States. Each factsheet provides a concise summary of the pilot's objectives, system design, influent type, treatment performance, co-benefits, and risk assessment results. Together, these factsheets offer an overview of each site's contribution to demonstrating the potential of nature-based solutions for decentralized urban water management.

France – INRAE – One stage hybrid treatment wetland treating raw wastewater

Photo INRAE

Courtesy of Ecobird

DESCRIPTION

Located in Craonne at the INRAE REFLET research platform in France, is a pilot-scale aerated hybrid treatment wetland designed to treat raw domestic wastewater from a combined sewer. Developed by EcoBird, the Rhizosph'air system consists of two parallel aerated wetland filters (20 m² total, serving approximately 25 population equivalents) connected at the saturated zone. The system enables simultaneous treatment of both wastewater and sludge and is engineered to perform reliably during extreme rainfall events.

DESIGN AND TECHNICAL DETAILS

Type of influent

Raw wastewater from a combine sewer facing loads and concentrations variations. Raw wastewater after a 40 mm screening.

Design criteria

- One stage of two parallel beds connected at the saturated zone. A first part of 20 cm depth is an unsaturated vertical flow system (only one bed in operation at the same time) and a second part of 1 m depth is an aerated horizontal flow system (the two beds are used continuously).
- Aeration is implemented by driplines positioned at the bottom of the filter (60 diffusers per m² – 1.5 m³.h⁻¹ per m²).
- Aeration can be controlled according to time, inflow or sensors.
- Influent COD is between 200–1,200 mg COD L⁻¹ and influent total nitrogen is between 25–120 mg N L⁻¹

Operational constraints

- **Loads and wastewater characteristic variations according to seasons and climatic conditions**
- **Routine maintenance of aeration system**
- **Vegetation maintenance : one harvesting per year**
- **Sludge maintenance: one emptying of mineralized and stabilized sludge every 10 to 15 years**

TREATMENT PERFORMANCES

- **Conventional Pollutants:** High removal of Total Suspended Solids (99%), COD (96%), and N-NH₄ (90%) and TN (81.4 %). Moderate removal of Total Phosphorus (15%).
- **Metals:** Removal of 70–90% for Cd, Cr, Fe, Cu, Zn, Al and 20–50% for Mn, Ni, and Se.
- **Organic Micropollutants:** Removal >90% for Caffeine, Atenolol, Benzoylcegonine, Mycophenolic acid, > 60 % for DEET, Benzotriazole, Gabapentin, lomeprol, Valsartan, Amoxicilin, 20–50 % for Venlafaxine, Diclofenac, Sotalol and Oxazepam.
- **Pathogens:** Moderate removal (around 2 log for E. Coli and Total Coliform).
- **Pathogens:** The annual risk of infection from an eventual reuse for toilet flushing is 0.927% for Escherichia coli and 0% for Salmonella.
- **Metals & Pharmaceuticals:** The treatment achieves a high-risk reduction (median: 86.9%). While the NBS effectively reduces risk, some compound levels remain non-negligible, requiring potential further treatment.

Outflow concentrations and removal efficiencies for high and normal inflow concentrations

CO-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Energy Savings: Up to 2 to 3 times lower electricity consumption than activated sludge. The system consumes around 1.5 kWh/kg of treated BOD₅ (1.8 for 500 PE, 1.3 for 1,000 PE and 1 for 4,000 PE) and around 0.5 kWh per cubic meter of treated water (0.7 for 500 PE, 0.5 for 1,000 PE and 0.4 for 4,000 PE).

Educational Value: Over 50 visitors, including students and professionals, promoting awareness of nature-based solutions.

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

- Compact configuration that delivers high-quality effluent for standard parameters and allows for flexible nitrogen removal through adaptable, on-demand aeration strategies.
- A resilient, cost-effective solution for decentralized wastewater treatment and potential reuse in urban environments.

LITERATURE

Miyazaki C. K., Morvannou A., Higelin E., Nivala J., Molle P. (2023) Aeration strategies and total nitrogen removal in a hybrid aerated treatment wetland. *Blue-Green Systems*, 5(2): 321–335. <https://doi.org/10.2166/bgs.2023.045>

Miyazaki C. K., Morvannou A., Petijean A., Nivala J., Molle P. (2024) Hydraulic characterization of a hybrid aerated vertical and horizontal treatment wetland. *Ecological Engineering*, Volume 206: 107301 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2024.107301>

USA – MSU – High Strength Wastewater

DESCRIPTION

The US pilot is specifically tailored for the treatment of high-strength domestic wastewater in a sub-freezing winter climate and is housed at the Bridger Bowl Ski Area, at 45.040 degrees N and an elevation of 1,960 meters. The ski area receives approximately 5 m of annual snowfall. The pilot receives clarified wastewater during the ski season, from December to April, with water temperatures of 2–4 °C. The pilot is a two-stage sub-surface vertical flow system with two parallel cells at each stage. The effluent of the second stage is recycled and independently applied to the first stage to facilitate complete nitrogen removal. Both stages were planted with two wetland plant species native to the northwestern United States, *Carex utriculata* (beaked sedge) and *Schoenoplectus acutus* (hardstem bulrush). The primary purpose of the partially saturated first stage is the removal of influent COD and the denitrification of nitrate recycled from the second stage effluent. The unsaturated second stage facilitates aerobic nitrification of influent ammonia to nitrate in the presence of low COD.

DESIGN AND TECHNICAL DETAILS

Type of influent

High-strength domestic wastewater from ski lodges including lavatories and kitchens

Design criteria

- Two-stage subsurface vertical flow system, 95 m² total
- First stage partially saturated to facilitate removal of NO₃⁻
- The effluent of the second stage is recycled to the first stage to facilitate complete nitrogen removal
- Influent COD is between 600–900 mg COD L⁻¹ and influent total nitrogen is between 150–200 mg N L⁻¹

Climatic conditions

The system operates during the winter ski season from December through April, when it is necessarily covered with snow and plants are dormant. The water temperature ranges from 2.5 – 5 °C

Operational constraints

Winter conditions with snowpack on surface

Freezing temperatures

Seasonal operation

TREATMENT PERFORMANCES

- ➔ **Conventional Pollutants:** Overall COD removal was >95%, TN removal was >70%, and ammonia removal was >97%.
- ➔ **Organic Micropollutants:** Thirty-eight CECs were detected in the influent wastewater over the 2022–23 operational season. Caffeine and gabapentin had the highest average influent concentrations. Lamiotrigine, amoxicillan, and iopamidol also had relatively high concentrations in the raw influent.
Six compounds detected in the influent were removed in the TW to levels below their detection limit: azithromycin, citalopram, clarithromycin, codeine T14, THC–COOH and trimethoprim.
- ➔ **Greenhouse Gases:** N2O, CH4 and CO2 emissions showed variable trends and emissions increased generally during dosing of wastewater onto the pilot. Emission factors were on the low end of measured GHG emissions for wastewater treatment processes.

CO-BENEFITS

RISK ASSESSMENT

Several chemicals exceeded their predicted no effect concentration in influent, mid-process and effluent (i.e. risk quotient > 1). The risk drivers were solely **organic chemicals** (i.e. pharmaceuticals and caffeine).

The treatment efficiency was generally high with risk reduction from influent to effluent of **78.6%** (median).

However, the exceedance of risk threshold was still 2–3 orders of magnitude in the effluent, likely due to the high-strength nature of the wastewater.

CHALLENGES

The primary challenges with operating a TW for ski resort wastewater treatment are:

Seasonal operation – the system operates four months of the year and is thus limited with respect to opportunities for data collection

Cold weather and freezing impacts on equipment and operators – air temperatures can drop to –40 °C. While the snow provides insulation from freezing, equipment can still be impacted by the cold and operators cannot always safely monitor and collect samples.

LITERATURE

S.H. Ayotte, C.R. Allen, A. Parker, O.R. Stein, E.G. Lauchnor, Greenhouse gas production from an intermittently dosed cold-climate wastewater treatment wetland, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 924, 2024, 171484, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171484>.

Stephanie H. Ayotte, Sarah J. Wallace, Christopher R. Allen, Kela P. Weber, Otto R. Stein, Ellen G. Lauchnor, Microbial community dynamics in a two-stage treatment wetland: Insights from treating seasonal ski resort wastewater, *Bioresource Technology Reports*, Volume 27, 2024, 101885, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2024.101885>.

Ayotte, S. H., Allen, C. R., Stein O. R., Lauchnor, E. G. Greenhouse emissions from a subalpine zone treatment wetland: Implications of mass transfer effects and sampling frequency. Submitted to *Ecological Engineering*.

Belgium – RIETLAND – Phytoparking treating pre-treated wastewater

Jaurrieta, Lide; «Illustrations of nature-based solutions for urban water management», <https://doi.org/10.34810/data1745>, CORA, Repositori de Dades de Recerca, V1

DESCRIPTION

Pilot 3 is a **Phytoparking** located in Ypres, Belgium, that treats wastewater of 105 PE in a septic tank followed by Phytoparking at an off-grid campsite. The Phytoparking is an **aerated hybrid wetland** that is covered with crushed gravel and grass tiles to support vehicles and other heavy objects. Rietland designed a system that treats black and grey water separately on 32m² and 44m², for **reuse for toilet flushing and agriculture**. The two systems are in **compliance with the Flemish government's** discharge limits (graph 1). The Phytoparking can handle load variations, making it appropriate for a campsite with high and low seasons (graph 2).

Additionally, **co-benefit** analysis shows that water can be **reused**, there are **no oil spills leaking** through Phytoparking, and **energy** consumption is **low**.

DESIGN AND TECHNICAL DETAILS

Build up: The Phytoparking consists of a 1.3m deep liner basin that is filled with expanded clay granulates (1m). There is no contact between groundwater and wastewater. On top of the substrate, a pressure-distributing layer and grass tiles are placed to support vehicles and other heavy objects.

Type of influent: Grey & Black domestic wastewater

Design Phytoparking

- Forced Bed Aerated – intermittent aeration
- Hybrid wetland of 44m² (grey) & 32m² (black) treats wastewater of 105 PE.
- Substrate = Expanded Clay Aggregates
- The treated grey water is reused for toilet flushing

Micropollutants: Due to the alternation between oxygen-rich and oxygen-poor conditions, a rich mosaic of bacterial life is created. This also efficiently removes pathogens and substances that are difficult to degrade, such as pharmaceuticals & insect repellents.

TREATMENT PERFORMANCES

- **Conventional Pollutants:** High removal > 90% of TSS, BOD, TP and NH₄ for grey and black water, High removal for TN (*G:71.2%/*B:71.0). High removal COD for black water (91.6%), and moderate for grey water (G:83.3%) graph 1.
- **Organic Micropollutants:** Grey: 8 substances found out of 25 (influent). Black: 21 substances found out of 44 (influent). Removal >80% for Valsartan, Rosuvatin, Propanolol, Losartan, Gabapentin, diclofenac and DEET; Irbesartan 33%
- **Pathogens:** High removal e-coli (G: log 4.8/B: log 4.0). Moderate removal for Total coliform (G: log 3.6/B: log 2.4) and Somatic coliphages (G: log 1.4/B: log 1.3).
- **Environmental impact:** Risk reduction of metals between influent and effluent is variable according to sampling dates and for different chemicals.

*G = Grey wastewater,

*B = Black wastewater

COD concentrations of black and grey wastewater influent and effluent over time. All effluent concentrations are below the purple line (Flemish limit for effluent:125mg/L).

VERSATILE SYSTEM

- **Robust System:** The Phytoparking is equipped with an intelligent controller that automatically adjusts the aeration to the amount of wastewater that is being treated. This further optimizes energy consumption and allows the Phytoparking to be used flexibly for varying loads and different types of wastewater. Graph 2 shows good COD removal at high loads – up to 2476 g/d – as well as at low loads in both grey and black water. The two influent concentrations of grey water showing only 55% removal were sampled during low season (low influent COD concentration of < 40 mg/L; Flemish effluent limit is 125mg/L). The Phytoparking is also very robust because there is seldom a malfunctioning, which means maintenance is limited.
- **Types of wastewater:** The Phytoparking can treat domestic wastewater and industrial wastewater such as from food and beverage industry, organic chemistry, soil remediation projects and wastewater flows from the agricultural sector.
- **Applications:** Residential areas, offices, hotels, campgrounds, hospitals, elderly homes, schools and businesses

Regardless the fluctuations in influent load of COD, the Phytoparking shows a good removal (range: 70% – 97%), not taking into account the two samples with influent concentrations (<40mg/L) during low season (Flemish limit for effluent:125mg/L).

REUSE LEGISLATION

WHO: The reclaimed water of the Phytoparking has no risk according to values for exposure by the WHO for **toilet flushing** and for irrigation of **lettuce for consumption** with grey water (tested for e-coli & Salmonella).

EU 2020/741: Monitoring over 2 consecutive years shows that effluent of the Phytoparking can be used for **agriculture** as reclaimed water quality class B.

EN16941-2: All treated grey and black water samples meet standards for NTU, pH & e-coli for **toilet flushing**, as well as the average values for Tot. Coliform. The reclaimed water of the Phytoparking does not meet the requirements for **water that is being sprayed**.

PROS AND COSTS

Advantages: Low operational costs, no skilled personal required, robust system, nice landscaping, does not add to urban heat island, does not require any space.

Costs:

- **OPEX low:** no sludge discharge, low energy consumption, only 1 annual maintenance
- **CAPEX moderate:** approximately €70.000 for 10 parking spaces that treat wastewater of 140 PE. The return on investment can be 5 years depending on the discharge levy.

CO-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

- **Water reuse:** 71% (389m³) of treated grey wastewater was reused for toilet flushing by 18071 camping guests.
- **Fluids leaking from vehicles:** A relatively large fraction of a potential oil spills is retained in the top layer. The large volume of the biofilter will assure dilution of the leakage so it will not impact the treatment performance. The micro-organisms can break down oil droplets.
- **Energy consumption:** 1224kWh (€355) was consumed to treat black and grey water from 18071 campsite guests during two camping seasons. The pump that facilitates the reuse of the reclaimed water requires 23% (276kWh) of the energy.

Italy – IRIDRA – Hybrid treatment wetland treating combined sewer overflows

Jaurrieta, Lide; Pueyo-Ros, Josep; Comas, Joaquim; Beral, Henry; Guillaume-Ruty, Sophie Hai Yen; Gonzalvo, Gisela, 2024, "Illustrations of nature-based solutions for urban water management", <https://doi.org/10.34810/data1745>, CORA.Repositori de Dades de Recerca, V1

DESCRIPTION

Located in Merone, Italy, Pilot 4 is a full-scale **aerated hybrid treatment wetland** aims to tackle **frequent and prolonged combined sewer overflows (CSOs)**, which can last for days and lead to untreated discharges into receiving waters, exacerbating pollution. Designed by IRIDRA in collaboration with COMO ACQUA and local stakeholders, the system integrates **aerated wetland beds** with a **surface flow wetland**, enhancing **pollutant removal efficiency** while keeping **operational costs low** compared to conventional infrastructure. Its high hydraulic flexibility allows it to adapt to intense weather events, making it a resilient solution for urban water management. Additionally, it delivers key **co-benefits**, including **cost savings, biodiversity enhancement, and educational value**.

DESIGN AND TECHNICAL DETAILS

Type of influent

CSOs with fluctuating pollutant loads.

Design

- Four aerated wetland beds covering 4,000 m².
- A 1,500 m² surface flow wetland for final polishing.
- Subsurface gravel layers and throttling valves for controlled infiltration and retention.
- Automated aeration and pumping system for optimized performance.

Cost

Up to 5x lower CAPEX & OPEX than grey infrastructure (€0.10/m³ vs. €0.46/m³).

Climatic conditions

Temperate climate with seasonal variations in rainfall affecting CSO frequency and composition.

Operational constraints

Land footprint:
Requires extensive space.

Biohazard
Pathogen risks in untreated CSOs require protective measures during maintenance.

Maintenance

Vegetation management
Periodic harvesting (1 per year).

Sludge control
Periodic removal of accumulated solids (1 every 10 years).

Aeration system upkeep
Regular cleaning and calibration.

TREATMENT PERFORMANCES

- **Conventional Pollutants:** High removal rates for Total Suspended Solids (TSS) (95.6%), COD (85.3%), and BOD5 (89.0%); moderate reductions in Total Nitrogen (31.9%) and Total Phosphorus (20.9%).
- **Metals:** Effective removal (70–90%) for cadmium, chromium, iron, copper, zinc, and aluminum; lower for manganese (29.9%), nickel (19.4%), and selenium (36.5%).
- **Organic Micropollutants:** Mixed performance, with high (>90%) removal for ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, mycophenolic acid, and citalopram, while some compounds like venlafaxine and carbamazepine showed limited removal.
- **Microplastics:** Strong retention (70–90%) for PMMA, nylon, polypropylene, PVC, and polystyrene; PET (~15–20%) had lower removal.
- **Pathogens:** Moderate reduction (0.5–2 log); E. coli (0.75 log), total coliforms (1.23 log), enterococci (2.16 log); Salmonella, Rotavirus, Adenovirus, and Enterovirus were not detected

RISK ASSESMENT

- **Pathogens:** The annual risk of infection from an eventual reuse for toilet flushing is 0.473% for Escherichia coli and 0% for Salmonella.
- **Metals & Pharmaceuticals:** The treatment achieves a moderate to high-risk reduction (median: 64.7%). Contrast agents pose no risk.
While the NBS effectively reduces risk, some effluent risk levels remain non-negligible, requiring potential further treatment.
- **Environmental Impact:** The overall risk is low, thanks to the dilution factor (medium risk for Se, As, Cd, Mn, and Zn).

CO-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

- Flood Reduction:** Reduces flood risk and prevents untreated discharges.
- Cost Savings:** Up to 5 times lower CAPEX & OPEX than conventional infrastructures.
- Biodiversity:** Enhances urban ecology, supporting bird diversity similar to semi-natural wetlands.
- Educational Value:** Over 100 visitors, including students and professionals, promoting awareness of nature-based solutions.

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

- **High treatment capacity:** Treated 400,000 m³/year (2023–2024) with stable performance.
- **Enhanced hydraulic efficiency:** Operated at 100–150 m/year HLR, exceeding passive wetland standards.
- **Effective pollutant removal:** High reduction of TSS, COD, BOD5, N-NH₄⁺, heavy metals, and microplastics.
- **Optimized aeration potential:** Performance results indicate potential for energy savings and efficiency improvements.

Spain – ICRA – GreenWall treating greywater

Jaurrieta, Lide; Pueyo-Ros, Josep; Comas, Joaquim; Beral, Henry; Guillaume-Ruty, Sophie Hai Yen; Gonzalvo, Gisela, 2024, «Illustrations of nature-based solutions for urban water management», <https://doi.org/10.34810/data1745>, CORA.Repositori de Dades de Recerca, V1

DESCRIPTION

Located in Sant Quirze del Vallès, Spain, Pilot 5, is a **full-scale horizontal flow green wall**, treating greywater from 3 showers and 2 handwash sinks in 3 different apartments, as well as rainwater collected from 120 m² of roof. Designed by Alchemia-nova, and put into place in April 2023, it is composed of 16 modules, each including 9 plant pods, with 5 plants per pod. It has a total treatment **surface of 10.94 m²**, combined with a further ozonation step, ensuring efficient pollutant and pathogen removal. It is designed to treat theoretically up to 220 L of greywater per day.

Additionally, it delivers key **co-benefits**, including **cost savings, biodiversity enhancement, and educational value.**

DESIGN AND TECHNICAL DETAILS

Type of influent

Greywater from three apartments.

Design

- Full-scale horizontal flow green wall, surface of 10.94 m².
- The green wall is combined with a further ozonation step.
- Once treated, the water is pumped back to the apartment to be reused for toilet flushing.

Cost

CAPEX is approximately €4,100 per m² of GreenWall, including all accessory equipment, OPEX is €0.34 per m³ of treated water. As a first-unit pilot, further optimization and cost reduction are possible.

Climatic conditions

A dry-temperate climate characterized by recurrent droughts. Temperate climate with seasonal variations in rainfall affecting the mixture between greywater and rainwater.

Operational constraints

Energy consumption:

Pumps for water circulation

Biohazard

Pathogen risks in untreated greywater require protective measures during maintenance.

Maintenance

Vegetation management

Periodic harvesting (1 per year).

Filters cleaning

Periodic cleaning of accumulated solids (1 per month).

Treated water tank cleaning

Periodic cleaning of accumulated solids (2 per year).

TREATMENT PERFORMANCES

- **Conventional Pollutants:** Significant removal of Ammonia (99%), BOD5 (98%), Total Suspended Solids (96%), COD (83%), TOC (80%), and Total Nitrogen (80%).
- **Organic Micropollutants:** Removal >90% of tramadol, THC-COOH and benzotriazole and 30–80% for DEET, caffeine and lidocaine.
- **Microplastics:** Removal of 70–99% on N66, PP, PVC, N6, SBR, PE, ABS and PS, and 50% removal of PET.
- **Pathogens:** High removal (>99%) of E.coli.

RISK ASSESSMENT

Organic micropollutants:

The treatment achieves a high risk reduction (median: 99.9%) of sum of risk posed by caffeine, lidocaine and DEET.

CO-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

New green areas: Add new green areas in urbanized contexts. They are aesthetically pleasing and give other environmental and social co-benefits.

Biodiversity: Supports species diversity, enhancing urban ecology and pollinator communities.

Stakeholder engagement: Promotes interaction among stakeholders with an open science approach. Located in a residential building, it highlights the crucial role of neighbours in both participation and the decision-making process.

Educational Value: Over 70 visitors, including students and professionals, promoting awareness of nature-based solutions.

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

- **On-site treatment:** Treatment sited in an urban environment with stable performance for a further reuse for toilet flushing.
- **Near zero spatial footprint:** Vertical technology with very low special requirements, ideal for urban contexts.
- **Effective pollutant removal:** High reduction of TSS, COD, BOD5, N-NH4+, TOC, TN and microbiological parameters.
- **Socioenvironmental impacts:** Aesthetic value and increase in urban biodiversity, making cities more drought resilient. Furthermore, community-based aspects, such as education and better well-being of the population.

Norway – Raingarden treating road runoff

Rodland, Elisabeth; Karlstrom, Stina; Tollefsen, Knut Erik; Moe, Jannicke; Meland, Sondre; Gragne, Ashenafi, Gjeitnes, Mari; Ribeiro, Anne Luise, Barkved, Line, 2025, «Illustrations of nature-based solutions for treating urban road runoff in Tåsen, Oslo; **A)** The road and the raingarden during a heavy rain event (August 2023), **B)** the raingarden and the influent monitoring box, **C)** sensors installed in the influent monitoring box, **D)** Illustration of raingarden with treatment from road runoff, **E)** the raingarden and the influent monitoring box showing water flowing over the v-notch».

DESCRIPTION

The Norwegian pilot is a **raingarden that treats runoff** along Tåsenveien in the City of Oslo. It was built as part of an upgrade in the area, where sidewalks and bike lanes on both sides of the road encourage more people to walk, cycle and travel by public transport. The upgrade project on Tåsenveien spans approximately 730 m and includes a stretch of road prone to flooding. It incorporates the planting of over 50 trees and the establishment of five separate rain gardens to **mitigate flooding and to treat runoff**. The pilot monitored is the first of the three rain gardens. The rain gardens are a good example of **nature-based solutions built to retain and remove pollutants** found in the road runoff so that they will not enter water pathways and eventually pollute the Oslofjord.

DESIGN AND TECHNICAL DETAILS

Type of influent

Urban stormwater, including runoff of from road, bike lanes and green areas.

Design criteria

- Impact area of raingarden about 1300 m².
- Raingarden area of about 60 m² offering a potential surface storage volume of about 19.6 m³ along its 33.5 m length.
- Road runoff enters the raingarden through two 20×15 cm inlet gutters located about 16 m apart.
- The inlet received 30m³ of road runoff in one year of monitoring (2023), whereas the outlet received 160m³.
- Automatic ISCO samplers placed at the influent and effluent of the raingarden have time-paced composite water samples at rainfall events.

Climatic conditions

Varied climate with seasonal variations in temperature (-23°C - 31°C) and precipitation (rain and snow).

Operational constraints

Manpower

Skills

Seasonal variations

TREATMENT PERFORMANCES

- **Conventional Pollutants:** Effective retention of TSS (88.5% reduction); Accumulation of total nitrogen, total phosphorous, P and Cl (120–1400% increase), where accumulation of Cl is most likely due to accumulation of road salt used during the winter.
- **Metals:** Effective retention potential for Al, Cr, Fe and Pb (60–90% reduction); Cu, Ni and W had lower retention potential (5–35% reduction); Cd, Na and Zn had a negative retention potential (24 – 244% increase), where accumulation of Na is most likely due to accumulation of road salt used during winter.
- **Organic Micropollutants:** Of 6 target compounds related to vehicle tires (6PPD, 6PPD-Q, ABT, BT, MBT, MTBT and OHBT), the average potential reduction in concentration was 73%.
- **Microplastics:** The average concentration of tire wear particles (TWP) was 2.57 ± 2.30 mg/L (average \pm SD) in the inlet and 0.488 ± 0.188 mg/L in the outlet (81% potential reduction).
- **Treatment efficiency:** Runoff is infiltrated to the ground and the estimated retention of pollutants based on inlet and outlet concentration data does not fully explain the treatment performance of the raingarden.

RISK ASSESMENT

- **Inlet:** With Cumulative Risk Assessment (CRA), 10 chemicals exceed the risk threshold – Al, 6PPD-quinone, Fe, Cu, Cl, Pb, fluoranthene, 2-(methylthio) benzothiazole, Zn and Na. Using Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) metals pose a 100% probability risk, and plastics pose 95%.
- **Outlet:** Using CRA, 7 chemicals exceed the risk threshold – Al, 6PPD-quinone, Cu, Cl, Zn and Na, where Na and Cl are due to road salt, and 6PPD-quinone and Zn are due to TWP. Using PRA, metals pose a 100% probability risk, and plastics pose 55%.
- **Treatment efficiency of rain garden:** CRA show a varied risk reduction efficiency of raingarden treatment from inlet to outlet due to sampling dates and emphasize the challenges with seasonal variations. Using PRA, 5 chemicals pose a substance level risk to the environment after raingarden treatment – Al, Cu, fluoranthene, 6PPD-quinone and Zn. The group risk sum indicates no environmental risk.

CO-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Environmental value:

Increased and preserved biodiversity and increased green infrastructure after establishment of raingarden compared to before development of Tåsenveien. Reduced flood risk, based on results from stress test of rain garden.

Socio-economic value:

Improved public health and well-being based on survey of public. Improved traffic safety from inspections of Tåsenveien.

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

- **Effective road runoff pollutant removal:** The rain garden had an effective retention potential of TWP and TWP-related compounds from inlet to outlet, and an effective retention potential of TSS and metals such as Al, Cr, Fe and Pb, and some retention potential of Cu, Ni and W.
- **Enhanced environmental and socio-economic value:** The rain garden, with its green infrastructure and enhanced biodiversity pose a positive value for the public, traffic safety and environment.
- **Optimized stormwater mitigation and flood risk:** A stress test of Tåsenveien demonstrated an optimized flood risk and storm water mitigation of the raingarden.
- **High treatment capacity:** The rain garden has an impact area of 1300 m², including road, parking lot, bicycle lane, park area and pedestrian lane. However, due to flaws in the inlet design, a significant proportion of road runoff bypasses the raingarden during heavy rainfall.

Germany – UFZ – Research green roof platform

Jaurrieta et al. (2024) CORA | Bernhard (2023) UFZ

DESCRIPTION

The UFZ Research Green Roof platform is tackling key urban challenges related to climate adaptation, exploring the **potential of multifunctional blue–green infrastructures**. The platform encompasses different blue–green infrastructures located at the UFZ campus Leipzig and in the city of Leipzig. The infrastructure platform includes different green roofs as well as tree swales. These systems contribute to **stormwater management**, mitigate urban heat through evapotranspiration, serve as sinks for CO₂ and airborne pollutants, and enhance **urban biodiversity** by providing habitats for plants and animals. Research at the UFZ focuses on optimizing blue–green infrastructures for a range of environmental and urban needs. This includes investigating their effectiveness in stormwater retention, temperature regulation, and improving urban microclimates. Researchers are also examining the most resilient plant species for green roofs, their role in supporting biodiversity, and their potential as decentralized treatment systems for low-polluted wastewater, such as greywater. In addition, studies are evaluating how different green roof types can act as pollution sinks, absorbing airborne contaminants, while reducing pressure on urban drainage systems. The UFZ Research Green Roof platform aims at providing long-term monitoring and performance metrics for blue–green infrastructure modeling & planning. As part of the performance metrics novel monitoring and modeling approaches are developed. Further the platform allows to operate the infrastructure under different functionalities and to investigate multifunctionality. In the framework of MULTISOURCE rainwater and overflow samples were collected from the green roofs and vegetation data were monitored for tree swales and urban trees.

DESIGN AND TECHNICAL DETAILS

Type of influent

- Rainfall

Design criteria

- Stormwater retention | biodiversity.
- Different vegetation mixes and soil depths.
- Different retention layer depths.
- Different management strategies (stormwater/ drought | irrigation | biodiversity).

Climatic conditions

Temperate climate with seasonal variations in rainfall.

Operational constraints

Manpower

Skills

Working in heights & potential constraints due to roof load

CO-BENEFITS

The UFZ blue-green infrastructure is open to researchers and practitioners as a research facility as well as a demonstration platform. Originally designed and operated towards biodiversity and stormwater, several studies across various disciplines have looked into multifunctionality and co-benefits. Co-benefits were extracted from the studies and systematically reviewing the key findings and the mentioned co-benefits. The **main themes – ecosystem services, climate adaptation, water resource management, air quality improvement, and building protection** – were identified across the studies. Key facts and outcomes of each study were highlighted, and the co-benefits were categorized into subcategories and overarching categories. Next to the co-benefit overview, the interlinkage with main functionalities – both in terms of **infrastructure design** as well in terms of **infrastructure operation** is essential. As an example, different irrigation schemes target different functionalities, i.e. biodiversity or cooling and affect stormwater functionality.

TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

- **Main functionalities** focus on stormwater mitigation & enhanced biodiversity
- **Multiple co-benefits** regarding ecosystem services, building management & maintenance, water resources management, climate adaption & mitigation, air quality & pollutant reduction, as well as health & social impacts were specifically addressed in over 15 studies at the UFZ platform.
- **Development of novel modeling and monitoring** approaches for blue-green infrastructures

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3. Overview of MULTISOURCE Pilots

MULTISOURCE pilots reflect a spectrum of NBS typologies, each tailored to a specific urban challenge. Designs range from hybrid treatment wetlands and raingardens to vertical green walls and research-grade green roofs. Despite their variety, these systems share a commitment to sustainability, decentralized treatment, and multifunctionality. The main design characteristics of each pilot, including treatment targets, configuration, and context, are summarized in Table 2.1.

Pilot 1 (France – INRAE), located at the INRAE REFLET research platform in Craaponne, France, is a hybrid treatment wetland designed for the treatment of raw domestic wastewater from a combined sewer. The system consists of a single-stage hybrid wetland, combining an unsaturated vertical flow zone (20 cm depth) with an aerated horizontal flow wetland (1 m depth). The influent is pre-screened (40 mm), with typical COD concentrations ranging from 200 to 1,200 mg/L and total nitrogen between 25 and 120 mg/L. Aeration is provided through 60 diffusers per square meter, delivering 1.5 m³/h per m² via driplines positioned at the base of the horizontal flow section. This configuration supports simultaneous treatment of organic matter and nutrients, while the flexible aeration system allows for adaptive nitrogen management depending on effluent quality targets.

Pilot 2 (USA – MSU) is specifically designed to treat high-strength domestic wastewater under sub-freezing winter conditions. It is located at the Bridger Bowl Ski Area in Montana (45.040°N, 1,960 meters elevation), which receives approximately 5 meters of snowfall annually. The system operates seasonally during the skiing season (December to April), treating clarified wastewater with influent temperatures ranging between 2–4 °C. The treatment system is a two-stage subsurface vertical flow wetland, with two parallel cells at each stage. Effluent from the second stage is recycled and reapplied to the first stage to enhance overall nitrogen removal. The first stage is partially saturated to promote COD removal and denitrification of nitrate from the recycled effluent. The second stage is unsaturated, allowing for aerobic nitrification of incoming ammonium under low COD conditions. Both stages are vegetated with native wetland species from the northwestern U.S., *Carex utriculata* (beaked sedge) and *Schoenoplectus acutus* (hardstem bulrush), selected for their adaptability to cold climates and high-altitude environments.

Pilot 3 (Belgium – Rietland) located in Ypres, Belgium, is a Phytoparking system designed to treat wastewater from an off-grid campsite serving approximately 105 population equivalents (PE). The system includes a septic tank followed by an aerated hybrid constructed wetland that is integrated beneath a reinforced surface of crushed gravel and grass tiles, allowing it to support vehicle traffic and heavy loads. Developed by Rietland, the design separates treatment of black water (32 m²) and grey water (44 m²), with treated effluent reused for toilet flushing and potential agricultural applications. Both treatment lines meet the Flemish discharge standards, and the system demonstrates strong resilience to seasonal load variations, which is essential for the fluctuating occupancy of a campsite. Co-benefit analysis highlights the degradation of oil spills in the treatment, the feasibility of water reuse, and the system's low energy consumption, making it a robust, multifunctional solution for decentralized sanitation.

Pilot 4 (Italy – IRIDRA), located in Merone, Italy, is a full-scale aerated hybrid treatment wetland designed to manage frequent and prolonged combined sewer overflows (CSOs), which can persist for days and result in untreated discharges into receiving water bodies. Developed by IRIDRA in collaboration with COMO ACQUA and local stakeholders, the system combines aerated vertical-flow gravel beds with a free water surface wetland, enhancing overall treatment efficiency while maintaining significantly lower operational costs compared to conventional infrastructure. The system's high hydraulic flexibility enables it to effectively manage variable inflows during extreme weather events, making it a resilient and adaptive solution for urban water management. In addition to pollutant reduction, the system offers important co-benefits, including substantial cost savings, increased biodiversity, and educational opportunities through public and professional engagement.

Pilot 5 (Spain – ICRA), located in Sant Quirze del Vallès, Spain, is a full-scale horizontal flow GreenWall system designed to treat greywater from three showers and two handwash basins across three residential apartments, along with rainwater collected from a 120 m² rooftop. Developed by Alchemia-nova and commissioned in April 2023, the system consists of 16 modular units, each comprising 9 plant pods with 5 plants per pod. The total planted treatment surface is 10.94 m², and the system includes an integrated ozonation step to enhance the removal of pollutants and pathogens. It is dimensioned to treat up to 220 liters of greywater per day. Beyond its treatment function, the GreenWall offers important co-benefits, including energy efficiency, urban greening, biodiversity support, and educational value, making it a multifunctional and visually integrated solution for decentralized water reuse in residential settings.

Pilot 6 (Norway – NIVA/Oslo Municipality) is a raingarden located along Tåsenveien in the City of Oslo, designed to treat urban runoff as part of a broader infrastructure upgrade aimed at promoting sustainable mobility. The redevelopment project spans approximately 730 meters and includes the installation of sidewalks and bike lanes on both sides of the road to encourage walking, cycling, and public transportation. This area is prone to flooding, and the project integrates five separate raingardens and over 50 newly planted trees to enhance stormwater management and urban resilience. The monitored pilot represents the first of the five raingardens and serves as a demonstrative example of nature-based solutions implemented to retain and treat road runoff. By capturing pollutants before they enter the water system, the raingarden contributes to protecting downstream ecosystems, including the Oslofjord.

Pilot 7 (Germany – UFZ) is a research-oriented green infrastructure platform based in Leipzig, designed to tackle key urban challenges related to stormwater management, climate adaptation, and ecological resilience. The platform integrates a range of blue-green infrastructure elements, including modular green roofs, tree swales, and retention beds, both at the UFZ campus and across the city. The green roof platform includes multiple configurations that vary in substrate depth (ranging from 1.7 to 15 cm), retention layer type (e.g. drainage layers, storage protection mats, and water storage mats), and vegetation types, including grasses, herbs, flowering species, sedum and *Phedimus* species, and marsh plants. Initial monitoring indicates a rainfall retention capacity of up to 95%, depending on storm intensity and system design. This aligns with findings from German studies, which report average annual retention rates of 50–60% for extensive green roofs, and up to 90% for intensive systems with deeper substrates (Forschungsgesellschaft Landschaftsentwicklung Landschaftsbau e.V., 2018). The platform also supports evapotranspiration-driven cooling, habitat provision, and decentralized stormwater storage. In addition, experimental modules test the treatment potential for greywater and support the cultivation of wetland-type vegetation under controlled conditions. Finally, it serves as a living lab for infrastructure modeling, multifunctionality testing, and urban sustainability planning. Collectively, these pilots span a wide spectrum of influent sources, hydraulic configurations, and operational strategies. They demonstrate the versatility of NBS to meet both local treatment needs and broader environmental goals, including water reuse, biodiversity enhancement, and urban livability. The main characteristics, treatment performance, co-benefits, and risk assessment results of the pilots are summarized in the individual factsheets provided in Section 2 of Deliverable D1.3 and available in report D1.2 (Carvalho et al., 2024).

Table 2.1: Overview of Pilot Design Characteristics.

Pilot	Area (m ²)	Water Type	Design Configuration	Key Features
France (1)	2 x 10	Raw domestic wastewater	Hybrid treatment wetland (vertical and aerated horizontal)	Treatment on demand, dynamic aeration, energy-efficient, high TN removal
USA (2)	95	High-strength ski wastewater	2-stage subsurface treatment wetland	Cold-resistant; effluent recirculation
Belgium (3)	76 (total)	Black & grey water	Phytoparking	Multifunctional black and grey water treatment
Italy (4)	5,500	Combined sewer overflows	Aerated treatment wetland + free water surface wetland	High hydraulic load resilience, optimized aeration patterns
Spain (5)	10.94	Greywater	GreenWall + ozonation	Urban vertical reuse; zero footprint
Norway (6)	60	Road runoff	Raingarden	Seasonal retention; tire wear focus
Germany (7)	Modular	Rain & greywater	Green roofs & swales	Multifunctional research platform

3.1 Common Challenges and Implementation Barriers

The implementation and operation of the seven MULTISOURCE pilots revealed some practical challenges, reflecting the complexity of deploying decentralized NBS in diverse urban contexts. Logistical constraints were common across pilots, particularly in cases where infrastructure had to be adapted to existing built environments or shared with other ongoing projects. Seasonal availability of influent water, especially in cold-climate or tourism-based locations, limited the duration and frequency of monitoring campaigns. In some cases, legal or administrative delays (such as intellectual property issues or the need to adjust technical designs due to local heritage regulations) also impacted pilot timelines.

Operational reliability and monitoring continuity presented further challenges. The installation and maintenance of online sensors required close coordination with local stakeholders, while systems with high infiltration rates or irregular inflows complicated performance assessments, particularly for removal efficiency calculations (i.e. difficulties in sampling the “same water” as inlet and outlet). Access limitations, harsh weather, and the need for frequent site visits to maintain vegetation and manage sludge also added to operational complexity. Unplanned changes made by local owners, such as adjustments to system settings, also posed a challenge, introducing variability in operating conditions and complicating data interpretation. These changes highlight the importance of clearly defined operational protocols and agreements, particularly in decentralized or shared-use settings.

Across several pilots, the need for strong local engagement was evident, not only to support technical monitoring but also to ensure system upkeep and long-term acceptance. Changes in ownership or institutional responsibility occasionally introduced uncertainty about system management and data continuity.

In addition to site-specific hurdles, several overarching implementation barriers were identified. These include the need for fit-for-purpose operational strategies adapted to urban environments, regulatory requirements for effluent disinfection under EU water reuse rules, and limitations on space availability for land-based NBS in dense cityscapes. Concerns over invasive species management, long-term maintenance responsibilities, and unclear governance frameworks also emerged as recurrent themes. In particular, the issue of ownership, of both the infrastructure and the data it generates, was noted as a key challenge affecting the durability and replicability of NBS across settings.

Despite these challenges, the pilots demonstrated that with careful design, adaptive planning, and committed stakeholder involvement, nature-based solutions can be effectively implemented in a wide range of urban scenarios.

4. Treatment Performances

4.1 Conventional Pollutants

Conventional pollutants, such as total suspended solids (TSS), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD₅), chemical oxygen demand (COD), ammonium (NH₄⁺), total nitrogen (TN), and total phosphorus (TP), remain key performance indicators for all wastewater treatment systems. Across MULTISOURCE pilots, these parameters were monitored extensively, and the results reflect both the maturity of nature-based treatment technologies and the importance of design tailoring to influent characteristics.

Several pilots demonstrated outstanding removal efficiencies for solids and organic matter. France (Pilot 1), USA (Pilot 2), Belgium (Pilot 3), and Spain (Pilot 5) reported removal rates exceeding 90% for TSS, BOD₅, and COD. This high level of performance can be attributed to the use of aerated or multi-staged wetland systems, which are particularly effective at supporting robust microbial communities capable of degrading organic contaminants. France's Rhizosph'air system, for example, includes two parallel aerated wetland filters with treatment-on-demand aeration, ensuring optimal oxidation of organics even under variable loading. The USA pilot, operating under cold conditions, uses a two-stage vertical flow configuration with effluent recycling between stages. These process designs are especially well-suited to high-strength or variable influents and illustrate the versatility of engineered wetlands in achieving consistent organic pollutant removal. Norway's pilot (Pilot 6), primarily focused on stormwater retention and the removal of emerging pollutants, demonstrated effective treatment of particulate matter, achieving 88.5% removal of TSS. The system was not designed to target nutrient removal, as road runoff typically contains low concentrations of nitrogen and phosphorus. The monitoring data indicated an accumulation of TN, TP, and chloride in the effluent, with increases ranging from 120% to 1400%. The elevated chloride levels are likely attributable to road salt application during winter months, highlighting the influence of seasonal de-icing practices on stormwater quality in cold-climate environments. Belgium's Phytoparking system also demonstrate significant treatment performances for conventional parameters, treating black and grey water in separate streams with intermittent aeration and intelligent flow control. The system achieved over 90% removal for TSS, BOD₅, COD, NH₄⁺, and TP in several sampling events, supported by high-load tolerance and stable operation across seasonal fluctuations. Spain's GreenWall pilot coupled with ozonation also achieved significant removal: 96% TSS, 98% BOD₅, and 83% COD, demonstrating that even space-constrained systems can deliver reliable treatment performances.

In terms of nitrogen removal, performance was more variable. The systems in France and USA demonstrated particularly high TN removal efficiencies, exceeding 80–90%. In both cases, design

features such as sequential nitrification and denitrification pathways, combined with controlled aeration or effluent recirculation, supported robust nitrogen transformation. Similarly, the Spanish pilot (pilot 5) proved high performance capacity, achieving 80% TN removal in a compact vertical GreenWall system designed for greywater reuse. The Belgian pilot, although smaller in scale, also achieved strong TN removal (approximately 71%) in both greywater and blackwater streams, suggesting efficient biological cycling within the substrate, particularly under favorable carbon-to-nitrogen (C:N) ratios. The Italian pilot treating CSOs exhibited moderate TN removal (~32%). This is likely linked to the dilute and variable nature of CSO influent, which typically has limited organic carbon and reduced hydraulic retention times. For the Norwegian and German pilots, nitrogen removal was not a primary treatment objective due to the nature of their influents (stormwater and rainwater) which typically contain low concentrations of nitrogen.

Phosphorus removal presents one of the most persistent challenges across all pilots. Most systems achieved modest reductions in TP, typically ranging from 15% to 35%, regardless of overall system performance for other parameters. An exception is Belgium, which reached ~90% TP removal, likely due to the use of expanded clay substrates with higher phosphorus sorption capacity, as well as controlled flow conditions that extend contact time. This demonstrates the importance of substrate selection in phosphorus dynamics within wetlands. In general, however, these findings suggest that unless designed with specific P-sorbing materials or chemical additives, nature-based systems may require polishing steps or complementary technologies to meet stringent phosphorus limits, particularly in reuse scenarios or sensitive receiving environments and keeping as target efficient removals also in long operational periods, when the saturation of adsorptive material could play negatively for this purpose.

Taken together, the pilots confirm that NBS systems are well suited for removing solids, organics, and ammonia, especially when enhanced with aeration or smart hydraulics. For nitrogen and phosphorus, performance hinges more critically on influent characteristics, media selection, and hydraulic retention, pointing towards the need for site-specific design optimization. The results reinforce the potential of these systems to form the backbone of sustainable urban water treatment, particularly when integrated into larger, modular treatments.

4.2 Organic Micropollutants

The removal of organic micropollutants (OMPs), such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, and industrial chemicals, was addressed in several of the MULTISOURCE pilot systems. Although the pilots differ in their water sources and design configurations, those that monitored OMPs offer valuable insights into the treatment potential and limitations of NBS for trace contaminants.

The French pilot (pilot 1) demonstrated a broad removal spectrum, achieving over 90% reduction for compounds like caffeine, atenolol, and mycophenolic acid, and more than 60% for others including DEET, gabapentin, and amoxicillin. This performance is likely linked to the system's aerated hybrid wetland design, which facilitates alternating redox conditions and allows for treatment-on-demand aeration strategies that enhance microbial degradation even for persistent organic compounds.

Pilot 2, treating high-strength wastewater from a ski resort in USA, identified thirty-eight compounds of emerging concern in the influent. Despite the challenges posed by cold temperatures, the system achieved complete removal (to below detection limits) for six substances, including azithromycin, citalopram, and THC-COOH, a secondary metabolite of tetrahydrocannabinol (THC). Caffeine and gabapentin, among the most concentrated pollutants, were significantly reduced, demonstrating the resilience of well-designed wetlands even under sub-freezing operational conditions.

In Belgium, the Phytoparking system (Pilot 3) also demonstrated strong performance in removing OMPs from both black and grey water. Removal efficiencies exceeded 80% for several widely used pharmaceuticals, including valsartan, propranolol, losartan, diclofenac, and the insect repellent DEET.

The system's design promotes alternating aerobic and anaerobic conditions, fostering a diverse microbial community capable of degrading persistent compounds. This redox-driven environment also supports effective pathogen reduction and enhances the breakdown of contaminants typically resistant to conventional treatment, such as OMPs.

Italy's pilot (pilot 4), designed to treat CSOs, reported variable outcomes. While certain antibiotics like ciprofloxacin and trimethoprim were effectively removed, persistent compounds such as venlafaxine and carbamazepine showed limited reduction, in line with the documented challenges in removing recalcitrant pharmaceuticals through passive or semi-passive treatment methods.

The Spanish GreenWall pilot presented a complementary approach by integrating an ozonation step following the biological treatment. This hybrid configuration allowed for more consistent high-level removal, with reductions greater than 90% for tramadol and benzotriazole. Moderately persistent substances like caffeine, lidocaine, and DEET were also removed to a considerable extent (30–80%). The use of post-treatment oxidation proved especially beneficial, as expected, in addressing compounds that are otherwise resistant to biological breakdown.

In Norway's raingarden (pilot 6), the system achieved an average concentration reduction of 73% across six target tire-related compounds, including 6PPD-Q, ABT, BT, MBT, MTBT, and OHBT, highlighting its potential to mitigate pollutants commonly found in road runoff.

Overall, these findings highlight the potential of NBS to mitigate a wide array of micropollutants, particularly when systems are tailored to promote redox diversity, extended retention times, and plant-microbe interactions. While easily degradable substances are reliably treated across most configurations, persistent compounds may require supplementary processes or further innovation in substrate and operational design. The pilots collectively underline that NBS can form a key component of urban water quality strategies, particularly when integrated into multi-barrier treatment chains.

4.3 Metals and Microplastics

The ability of NBS to retain heavy metals and emerging contaminants like microplastics is gaining increasing attention, and several MULTISOURCE pilots provide informative case studies on this front. While the scope and depth of monitoring vary, pilots in France, Italy, Norway, Belgium, and to some extent Spain and Germany, reported valuable findings related to the retention of metals and synthetic polymers.

Heavy metal removal was found to be particularly effective in systems that incorporated gravel, clay, or other adsorptive multi-layer substrates. The French pilot (pilot 1), utilizing a compact aerated hybrid wetland, reported removal rates ranging between 70–90% for key metals such as cadmium, chromium, iron, copper, zinc, and aluminum. In contrast, elements like manganese, nickel, and selenium exhibited more moderate retention (20–50%), which is consistent with their higher mobility and lower binding affinity to particulate media. The system's aeration strategies and substrate composition likely contribute to both redox-driven precipitation and filtration processes. Similarly, the Italian pilot (pilot 4) treating CSOs achieved strong metal removal with effectiveness again ranging from 70–90% for cadmium, chromium, iron, copper, zinc, and aluminum. Manganese, nickel, and selenium removal in this system remained limited. Interestingly, the pilot also noted that certain metals, such as arsenic and selenium, posed low environmental risk due to post-treatment dilution effects, even when present in residual concentrations. Norway's raingarden (pilot 6) offers an urban stormwater application of NBS and reported a comparable range of results. High retention (60–90%) was achieved for aluminum, chromium, iron, and lead, while copper, nickel, and tungsten showed more modest reductions (5–35%). Certain elements, including cadmium, sodium, and zinc, showed increased concentration in the effluent, likely due to road salt use and mobilization of fine sediments during rainfall events. These findings underscore the seasonal variability and operational sensitivity of raingarden systems when exposed to winter deicing products. Belgium's Phytoparking pilot (pilot 3),

while primarily designed for domestic wastewater, also demonstrated capacity for metal attenuation. The expanded clay aggregates used in the subsurface layers contribute to adsorption and filtration of dissolved metals, enhancing overall pollutant removal. However, monitoring also indicated that the Argex substrate can contribute to the leaching of certain metals and the release of sulfate under specific conditions. This dual behavior highlights the importance of substrate selection and long-term monitoring to ensure that the system consistently delivers net environmental benefits.

Microplastics and tire-wear particles (TWP) were addressed specifically by the pilots in Italy and Norway, positioning them at the forefront of this increasingly critical area. Italy's hybrid wetland system (pilot 4) achieved strong retention (70–90%) of a wide range of microplastic polymers, including PMMA, nylon, polypropylene, PVC, and polystyrene. Lower removal was reported for PET, a less dense polymer, which tends to remain suspended in water columns. These findings highlight the physical capture potential of vegetated and stratified flow systems for solid microparticles. Similarly, pilot 5 from Spain proved a removal of 70-99% several polymers, including N66, PP, PVC, N6, SBR, PE, ABS and PS, and 50% removal of PET. Norway's raingarden (Pilot 6) demonstrated effective retention of TWPs, with an average reduction of 81% over the sampling period, decreasing from 2.57 ± 2.30 mg/L at the inlet to 0.488 ± 0.188 mg/L at the outlet. The green roofs studies in Leipzig (Pilot 7) focused on stormwater management and not on classic treatment. At the same time the microplastic results (see D1.3) show an increase in microplastics compare to the rainfall influx. Whereas this is logical as the green roofs include plastic material (e.g. liners, drainage mats) it is a valuable background signal as the basic materials (e.g. gravel, substrate, liners, drainage mats, pipes) are similar to those used in treatment systems. It is, however, important to point out that this should not result in a negative impression towards NBS, as the classic grey infrastructures (sewer systems, conventional treatment plants) have the same materials and are implemented at much larger scales.

Collectively, the pilot findings demonstrate that NBS systems can achieve substantial removal of heavy metals and synthetic particulates when configured with optimized substrate compositions and hydraulically controlled flow regimes. While removal efficiencies are compound-specific, reflecting differences in solubility, particle size, and affinity for sorptive media, the results underscore the capacity of NBS to function as effective sinks for both legacy and emerging urban pollutants. These outcomes reinforce the strategic relevance of NBS in advancing integrated, decentralized approaches to urban water quality management.

4.4 Pathogens

Pathogen removal is a critical indicator of treatment safety, particularly for systems intended for water reuse. Across the MULTISOURCE pilots, microbiological performance was assessed using log reduction values and quantitative risk analyses, revealing a broad range of outcomes. These variations reflect differences in influent composition, system design, multi-barrier configurations, and the inclusion of post-treatment processes.

An effective pathogen removal was observed in Belgium (Pilot 3) and Spain (Pilot 5). Belgium's Phytoparking system, treating grey and black water streams separately, achieved log reductions of up to 4.8 for *E. coli* in greywater and 4.0 in blackwater. The system's forced-aeration and treatment layer (LECA) likely contributes to both biological inactivation and physical filtration of microbial contaminants. Spain's vertical GreenWall system, which treats greywater from residential buildings, achieved a log reduction of 2 in *E. coli*, supported by a post-treatment ozonation step. The combination of biological processes with oxidative disinfection appears particularly effective for producing reclaimed water suitable for reuse in toilet flushing. Belgium and Both Belgium and Spain demonstrated compliance with the quality standards for Class B reclaimed water under EU Regulation 2020/741. In Belgium, both greywater and blackwater streams met the required thresholds, while in Spain, only greywater was evaluated and shown to meet Class B standards. This qualifies the treated water for uses such as surface irrigation and, under Spanish national legislation (RD 1085/2024), for

toilet flushing applications. These achievements highlight the viability of decentralized nature-based systems in producing water safe for reuse, especially when multi-barrier approaches, including physical filtration, aeration, and disinfection, are integrated into system design.

Moderate reductions were reported in France (Pilot 1) and Italy (Pilot 4). The French hybrid wetland, treating raw domestic wastewater, achieved approximately 2-log reductions in *E. coli* and total coliforms. Italy's pilot, designed for intermittent CSOs, reported similar log reductions ranging from 0.75 to 2.16 for various pathogens including *E. coli*, coliforms, and enterococci. While effective for reducing the microbial loads typically discharged by CSOs in the receiving water bodies, enhancing as a consequence their overall quality status and reducing risks linked to the quite common practices of indirect reuse for agricultural plots irrigation, the residual concentrations may still pose risk in direct reuse scenarios without further treatment.

Pathogen removal across the MULTISOURCE pilots is closely tied to treatment configuration and intended use. While most systems reduce microbial risk to acceptable levels for non-potable applications, achieving higher classes of water reuse often requires additional barriers or more intensive approaches. The results confirm that with careful design and operational oversight, NBS can meet both environmental and health-related performance targets in urban water management.

5. Risk Assessment

Risk assessment forms a critical component of evaluating the feasibility and safety of water reuse, particularly when dealing with treated effluents containing trace levels of pathogens, heavy metals, or pharmaceuticals. The MULTISOURCE assessments not only provide insight into the safety of individual pilots but also serve as an important benchmark for positioning NBS within national and international water reuse frameworks.

Across the pilots, most of the systems achieved risk reductions exceeding 70%, with some reporting mitigation above 85%. In France (Pilot 1), quantitative microbial risk assessment (QMRA) estimated the annual infection risk associated with reusing treated water for toilet flushing at 0.927% for *Escherichia coli* and 0% for *Salmonella*. While the *E. coli* risk slightly exceeds the WHO's tolerable threshold (0.1–1% depending on end use), it remains within a manageable range for non-potable applications, particularly when supported by additional barriers or treatment steps. The French pilot also demonstrated a median 86.9% reduction in overall chemical risk, including metals and pharmaceuticals, reinforcing the mitigation potential of hybrid wetland treatment systems.

The risk assessment of Italian CSO-CW (Pilot 4) indicates that the system provides a significant reduction in both microbiological and chemical risks. For pathogens, the estimated annual infection risk associated with potential reuse for toilet flushing is 0.473% for *Escherichia coli* and 0% for *Salmonella*, remaining within acceptable limits for non-potable reuse under international guidelines. In terms of chemical contaminants, the treatment system achieves a moderate to high reduction in overall risk, with a median risk reduction of 64.7%. Contrast agents, often considered persistent, were found to pose no risk in this context. While the NBS effectively mitigates most risks, some residual concentrations, particularly of certain pharmaceuticals and trace metals, suggest that complementary polishing steps may be needed if higher reuse standards are to be met. From an environmental perspective, the overall impact is considered low, largely due to the buffering effect of dilution in the receiving environment. However, moderate risk levels remain for elements such as selenium, arsenic, cadmium, manganese, and zinc, warranting further attention depending on local discharge requirements.

In Spain (Pilot 5) and Belgium (Pilot 3), the emphasis on pathogen removal and system reliability enabled their treated effluents to meet both national (RD 1085/2024 in Spain) and EU Water Reuse Regulation (2020/741) criteria for Class B reclaimed water, which is suitable for applications such as toilet flushing and crop irrigation under specific control measures. In Spain, the integration of

ozonation ensured that microbial risks were nearly eliminated, with *E. coli* levels consistently falling below detection limits in most samples. In Belgium, the Phytoparking system achieved high microbial inactivation in both greywater and blackwater streams, supported by a design that features separate treatment lines for each stream and intelligent aeration control. Risk assessments in Belgium confirmed that the reclaimed water posed no significant health risk, even under conservative exposure scenarios. Specifically, the system was found to be safe for daily and annual exposure through toilet flushing (for *E. coli* and *Salmonella*) and for the consumption of lettuce irrigated with treated greywater, in line with World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines. Both systems also evaluated the risk of exposure through aerosolization or contact in reuse applications, consistently demonstrating that under typical operating conditions, the associated health risks remained acceptably low. The USA pilot (Pilot 2), operating in a high-strength and cold-climate environment, highlighted the complexity of chemical risk profiles. Risk assessment revealed that several chemicals, primarily organic compounds such as pharmaceuticals and caffeine, exceeded their predicted no-effect concentrations (risk quotient >1) across all treatment stages, including influent, mid-process, and effluent. Despite this, the treatment system demonstrated strong overall performance, achieving a median risk reduction of 78.6%. However, residual risk in the effluent remained 2–3 orders of magnitude above threshold values, likely reflecting the high-strength nature of the incoming wastewater.

In Norway (Pilot 6), risk assessment of the raingarden highlights notable reductions in environmental risk, though some pollutants remain of concern. At the inlet, ten substances, including several metals, road salts, and tire wear-related compounds, exceeded risk thresholds according to Cumulative Risk Assessment (CRA). Probabilistic Risk Assessment (PRA) confirmed a 100% probability of risk from metals and 95% from plastics. At the outlet, the number of substances exceeding CRA thresholds dropped to seven, with road salt and tire wear particles still contributing significantly. While metals continued to pose a 100% risk probability, the risk from plastics decreased to 55%. Overall, the treatment performance of the raingarden varied seasonally, with some pollutants, such as aluminum, copper, zinc, and 6PPD-quinone, still exceeding environmental thresholds. However, the combined group risk was considered low, suggesting that despite persistent individual contaminants, the system provides meaningful environmental protection on a broader scale.

The results obtained by MULTISOURCE pilots confirm that NBS systems, when appropriately designed and maintained, can support safe and context-sensitive water reuse. Many of the pilots meet or approach key health benchmarks set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the European Union and demonstrate that even decentralized systems can be aligned with modern water reuse regulations. Where residual risks remain, whether microbiological or chemical, they can be addressed through modular enhancements such as polishing steps, disinfection, or dilution-based management strategies.

6. Environmental and Social Co-Benefits

Although pollutant mitigation remains the primary objective, the broader environmental and social co-benefits delivered by the MULTISOURCE pilots are integral to their long-term impact and potential for replication. NBS have demonstrated to support biodiversity, enhance climate resilience, foster community engagement, reduce costs, and contribute to urban resilience (cf. Pilot 7, Moeller et al. 2025). The assessment of the seven pilots highlighted a diverse range of co-benefits, each shaped by the specific context and configuration of the implemented system.

Biodiversity enhancement emerged as a defining co-benefit, particularly in systems designed to integrate natural habitat elements. The Italian pilot (Pilot 4), a hybrid wetland treating CSO, supported bird diversity comparable to that of semi-natural wetlands. This high biodiversity is likely due to the combination of aerated beds and free water surface zones, which create varied microhabitats and support passive colonization, as well as the large size of the system, which offers sufficient space for

ecological development. Similarly, the German pilot (Pilot 7) was explicitly designed to optimize urban biodiversity through a network of modular green roofs and tree swales. These systems form part of an ongoing ecological research platform, supporting studies on arthropod diversity, plant succession, and pollinator dynamics in urban environments.

Flood mitigation and climate resilience were strongly demonstrated in the Norwegian and Italian pilots. In Oslo (Pilot 6), the raingardens implemented along a residential street corridor significantly reduced peak flows during rainfall events, confirmed through targeted stress tests. These vegetated systems also contributed to localized cooling and improved urban microclimates. In Italy (Pilot 4), the wetland system played a critical role in buffering stormwater surges and preventing untreated discharges during combined sewer overflow events, effectively reducing flood risks in urban catchments.

Thermal comfort, shading, and air quality improvements were key benefits observed in the Spanish and German pilots. In Spain (Pilot 5), the vertical GreenWall contributed to reducing heat gain on the building façade, improving interior comfort and contributing to energy savings. Meanwhile, Germany's green roofs (Pilot 7) provided evaporative cooling, stormwater retention, and insulation, alongside measurable reductions in airborne particulate pollutants. These systems demonstrate how NBS can contribute not only to environmental goals but also to health and wellbeing in dense urban areas.

Public engagement and educational outreach were integral to several pilots and were especially prominent in France and Spain. The French pilot (Pilot 1), installed at INRAE's REFLET platform, welcomed over 50 visitors including students, researchers, and local officials, serving as a compact, functional demonstration of hybrid wetland technologies. In Spain, the GreenWall pilot (Pilot 5) attracted more than 70 visitors and served as a WP1 Living Lab for stakeholder co-design and evaluation. Importantly, it supported the collection of gender-responsive and wellbeing indicators, reinforcing the social relevance of urban green infrastructure. In Italy, Pilot 4 also demonstrated strong outreach value, with over 100 visitors participating in guided tours and site visits, ranging from academics to municipal stakeholders.

Energy efficiency and operational simplicity were critical in supporting decentralized applications and long-term sustainability. Belgium's Phytoparking system (Pilot 3) treated wastewater for over 18,000 seasonal visitors while consuming only 1,224 kWh across two seasons. This low energy demand, combined with minimal maintenance needs, made it particularly attractive for remote or seasonal deployment. The French (Pilot 1) and Spanish (Pilot 5) pilots also highlighted their low energy profiles and robustness, showcasing the technical viability of NBS under varying climatic and hydraulic conditions. In addition, the USA pilot (Pilot 2) provided valuable data on greenhouse gas emissions from high-strength wastewater treatment in cold climates, supporting climate-related performance monitoring for NBS. Emissions of key greenhouse gases, nitrous oxide (N₂O), methane (CH₄), and carbon dioxide (CO₂), showed variable trends, generally increasing during dosing events when fresh wastewater was applied to the system. Despite these fluctuations, the calculated emission factors remained on the lower end of reported values for wastewater treatment processes, suggesting that the pilot's design supports relatively low carbon intensity while maintaining treatment performance. Furthermore, in Italy, Pilot 4 demonstrated to operate at up to five times lower capital and operational costs (CAPEX and OPEX) compared to conventional gray CSO treatment infrastructure. This level of cost efficiency enhances the case for broader adoption of NBS, particularly in budget-constrained municipalities or as part of climate-resilient infrastructure planning.

Policy integration and multifunctional urban design were emphasized in pilots from Germany and Norway. The German pilot contributed to long-term research on ecosystem services and informed planning strategies for green roofs and sustainable building design. In Oslo, the raingarden installation was embedded within a municipal redevelopment corridor, serving not only as a stormwater

management tool but also as a prototype for city-wide NBS integration in future road and infrastructure upgrades.

Support for water reuse and circularity was also a clear co-benefit in several sites. The Belgian pilot (Pilot 3) enabled toilet flushing reuse after treating greywater from camping facilities, while the Spanish GreenWall (Pilot 5) met national and EU requirements for greywater reuse in residential settings. These systems demonstrate how NBS can contribute to local resource efficiency and sustainable water management at building or community scale.

In summary, the MULTISOURCE pilots demonstrate that, alongside decentralized water treatment, nature-based solutions can deliver a wide range of co-benefits, including enhanced biodiversity, reduced environmental and climate risks, improved urban comfort and livability, increased public awareness and engagement, and greater energy and cost efficiency. These co-benefits are essential not only for stakeholder acceptance and policy support but also for scaling and replicating nature-based solutions across diverse urban environments in Europe and beyond.

7. Main outcomes

MULTISOURCE pilots represent a rich and diverse demonstration of how NBS can be effectively tailored to address a wide range of urban water management challenges. From greywater recycling and high-strength wastewater treatment to stormwater retention and CSO mitigation, the pilots collectively showcase the adaptability, functionality, and multi-benefit potential of decentralized, ecological treatment systems.

Across the seven pilots, several key conclusions emerge. The systems consistently delivered strong performance in removing conventional pollutants. Many pilots exceeded 90% removal rates for TSS, BOD₅, and COD, even under challenging conditions such as cold climates or fluctuating inflows. These outcomes show how NBS can meet, and often exceed, the basic treatment expectations traditionally associated with centralized infrastructure. While performance in nitrogen and phosphorus removal was more variable, pilots that incorporated advanced design features, such as staged aeration, effluent recirculation, or specific P-sorbing media, demonstrated the ability to address nutrient challenges effectively. However, phosphorus removal remains a common limitation in many systems, indicating a need for either substrate optimization or additional polishing steps where nutrient standards are especially stringent.

Additionally, the pilots provided important insight into the treatment of emerging contaminants. Several systems achieved notable reductions in pharmaceuticals, personal care products, microplastics and tire-wear particles. Although some persistent compounds proved difficult to remove fully, the evidence suggests that hybrid systems and post-treatment enhancements (e.g. ozonation) can significantly improve overall removal and risk reduction.

Pathogen control represented a notable achievement across several pilots, with multiple systems demonstrating log reduction levels consistent with WHO and EU standards for non-potable water reuse. Notably, the Belgian and Spanish pilots consistently produced Class B reclaimed water according to EU water reuse legislation, making it suitable for applications such as irrigation, and according to national rules, also for toilet flushing, thereby supporting the feasibility of safe, decentralized reuse strategies. Quantitative risk assessments further indicated that residual health risks were generally within acceptable limits or could be effectively managed through targeted operational adjustments.

Beyond treatment performance, the pilots revealed the broader ecological and social value of NBS. They contributed to urban biodiversity, reduced flood risk, improved microclimates, and served as platforms for public engagement and education. Their aesthetic qualities and minimal energy demands enhanced their suitability for integration into both residential and public spaces. By

delivering tangible co-benefits alongside robust water treatment, these systems exemplify the multifunctionality that is central to sustainable urban infrastructure.

MULTISOURCE pilots underscore the importance of context-specific, flexible design in achieving long-term system resilience. Engaging local actors throughout the design and operation phases helped ensure both technical robustness and social acceptance. The integration of real-time monitoring tools supported adaptive management and optimization.

To support the broader adoption of NBS, several practical recommendations emerge:

- Municipalities should integrate modular, flexible designs that allow for incremental scaling.
- Utilities and designers should prioritize energy-efficient aeration and data-driven operational strategies.
- Regulatory bodies should update reuse guidelines to reflect the capabilities of modern NBS.
- Planners are encouraged to include co-benefit frameworks during early project stages to enhance multifunctionality and funding eligibility.

8. Future perspectives and Knowledge Transfer

As the MULTISOURCE project approaches its conclusion, a key focus is ensuring that the knowledge, tools, and lessons learned from the pilot activities are shared widely and used to inspire future action. Some pilots (e.g. Pilot 7) are also accessible by the public and are, next to being a research platform, used as demonstrators for stakeholders and colleagues. The pilot factsheets included in Section 2 provide a clear and accessible summary of each system's objectives, design, performance, and benefits. Although scientifically robust, the materials are designed to be accessible to a diverse stakeholder group, including technical experts, municipal authorities, urban planners, and non-specialist end users. Scientific publications focusing on individual pilot outcomes and cross-pilot synthesis are published (Moeller et al. 2025) or currently in preparation.

A comprehensive overview of design characteristics and treatment performance across various contaminant classes, including emerging pollutants, pathogens, and heavy metals, is provided in report D1.2, published on the Zenodo platform (Carvalho et al., 2024).

9. References

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The overall goal of MULTISOURCE is to, together with local, national, and international stakeholders, demonstrate a variety of about Enhanced Natural Treatment Solutions (ENTS) treating a wide range of urban waters and to develop innovative tools, methods, and business models that support citywide planning and long-term operations and maintenance of NBSs for water treatment, storage, and reuse in urban areas worldwide. The project includes seven pilots treating a wide range of urban waters. Two individual municipalities (Girona, Spain; Oslo, Norway), two metropolitan municipalities (Lyon, France; Milan, Italy), and international partners in Brazil, Vietnam, and the USA will contribute to each of the main project activities: ENTS pilots, risk assessment, business models, technology selection, and the MULTISOURCE Planning Platform. The use of urban archetypes in the Planning Platform will enable users to quickly classify regions (in both developed or developing countries) suitable for the application of NBSs for water treatment (NBSWT) and compare scenarios both with and without NBSWT.

MULTISOURCE
enhanced natural treatment solutions

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